

Hello,

As part of our Master's thesis at Blekinge Institute of Technology, our research investigates how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in FOSS/OSS dependencies they include in their projects. Considering that software supply chain attacks have become more frequent in recent years, understanding how developers' awareness of the risks linked to having vulnerable dependencies in their dependency trees is vital for the open-source community and the global software development community that relies on FOSS/OSS, as well as for the users of software supported by FOSS/OSS. Your participation in this research will help us understand how developers manage dependencies in their projects. The study focuses on developers from these ecosystems and web frameworks: Python (Django), JavaScript (Next.js), Java (Spring Boot), PHP (Laravel), and Ruby (Ruby on Rails).

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Your name, role, email address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you are not comfortable answering. Your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the project(s) you represent. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the reported data, after which they will be deleted.

Questions

- 1. Please introduce yourself and the project(s) you are a developer, contributor, or maintainer of. (Projects based on the main framework are also accepted, e.g., a maintainer or contributor for django-debug-toolbar but not Django itself, or if you develop using Django).**

For this, you can mention the project(s), how long you have been involved with it/them, and how you contribute to it, that is, are you a developer, maintainer, contributor, owner, admin, etc. This is meant to help us get to know you without you having to provide any identifying personal information. Also, mention your job title.

I have been involved in Django as a contributor participating in ticket triage, authoring pull requests and reviewing other people's pull requests. In my day job I am an independent contractor on an academic Django project.

2. What is your role in the project(s)?

Options can be: Contribute code, Tester, Triage issues to accept tickets, Review pull requests, Merge pull requests, Decide on software design, Decide on security issues:

Contribute code, ticket triage, reviewing pull requests

3. How is the project(s) you are working on governed?

Options can be: Corporate company; A non-profit foundation; Community-driven, with a registered non-profit foundation; Community-driven without a registered foundation/corporate company; Corporate company is managing the FOSS/OSS project; Creators or maintainers (a few individuals)

Community driven with an registered non-profit

4. Are there any governance structures or teams within your project responsible for security issues within your project?

This is a follow-up to the question regarding the project's governance. For example, some projects have separate technical boards/steering councils and security teams. You can share details on those structures and share which ones you participate in.

Yes. There is a security team and they operate in private.

5. From which ecosystem do(es) your project(s) belong to?

Options are: Python, Java, JavaScript, PHP, Ruby

Python

6. Which web framework do(es) your project(s) belong to?

Options are: Django, Spring Boot, Next.js, Laravel, Ruby on Rails

Django

7. How many years of experience do you have with the framework?

If I count hobby projects that's over 5 but I have 2 years of professional experience.

8. Which other ecosystems does your project rely on?

Python, Java, JavaScript, PHP, Ruby – if you use dependencies from other ecosystems.

Javascript

9. How are security issue reports managed in your project(s)?

The question seeks to understand how your project handles security reports within the project(s) you maintain for vulnerabilities discovered within your project(s). This question focuses on the vulnerabilities in your project code or CI/CD scripts for infrastructure definitions, and how they are handled from the time they are reported through their resolution and publication as CVEs.

Security reports are triaged, reviewed and fixed by a private experienced team in the DSF. Since recently, Django has become it's own CVE numbering authority, so I think that CVE's are published only when they have verified a vulnerability and published a security release.

10. How conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your projects?

I am not conscious of specific vulnerabilities in the dependencies of the project. Sometimes I look at the security releases to see what vulnerabilities have been fixed, so I guess I could say that I am only aware of vulnerabilities after the fact. But for projects that I work on as an independent contractor, I always check how active the development of open source dependencies is, who is contributing them and are they experienced in the industry, have they earned trust, do they have security releases. At the very least, they should be actively upgrading their own dependencies and releasing security or minor releases with that take advantage of upstream security patches in Python and Django and other major dependencies.

**11. How aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects?
How conscious are you of the risks that dependencies create in relation to supply chain threats?**

I'd say I have at best a vague awareness that such a thing exists.

12. How do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your projects?

The question seeks to understand which tools or automation your projects have in place to identify vulnerable dependencies. It also seeks to understand how you become aware of CVEs published by the dependencies you use in your project. FOSS/OSS projects can also be taken over by malicious actors, who may use them to launch supply chain attacks.

13. What influences the decision to update to newer versions of the dependencies within your projects?

The question seeks to understand the decision-making process for upgrading dependencies from pinned versions when vulnerabilities are discovered.

14. How do you track the maintenance of dependencies in your projects?

This question aims to understand whether developers oversee dependencies within their projects. Some dependencies become outdated and abandoned, and their vulnerabilities are never addressed.

For Django, I track the maintenance by actively contributing. But for Python, I usually just upgrade to the newest version of Python following Django's latest supported version. Since I do not have much experience with security issues myself, I trust the Django contributors and maintainers who I work with, and whose expertise I know quite well, on security matters. The core team is actively involved with CVEs related to upstream Python and other dependencies that Django uses. Knowing this allows me to trust the security in Python and Django and to focus on checking for vulnerabilities in third-party packages that I use on top of Django and Python.

15. How do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your project?

This question seeks to understand whether vulnerable dependencies are always updated and what happens when there is no newer version to upgrade to.

I always upgrade to more secure versions. But I have come across projects where it was not easy to upgrade the dependencies, for example, because a project was years behind in security updates. In that case the way forward would be to accept the temporary vulnerability and plan an upgrade. If possible, an additional measure would be to patch the dependencies and use patched versions.

16. How long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

This question seeks to understand the resolution times, from the moment a dependency is identified as vulnerable to the time an upgrade or removal is performed.

That depends on the severity of the vulnerability. The higher the severity the quicker the response. Quick responses can happen in a few hours, while other issues can take an entire release cycle to get fixed because an attack would be low impact.

17. How do you handle vulnerable dependencies that are no longer being maintained?

It is common for FOSS/OSS projects to become unmaintained. This question seeks to understand how developers handle dependencies that are no longer maintained.

I handle this by switching to newer, better-maintained packages. So far I have always been able to find them. If time allows and I am familiar enough with the project, I would consider participating in the maintenance of the dependency, say, in a fork.

18. For dependencies within your ecosystem, taking over abandoned projects which you have as dependencies and heavily rely on may be a consideration. How difficult is this when the dependency is outside of your ecosystem? For example, a deprecated JavaScript library used in a Django project.

This is difficult. I try to keep away from using libraries that I do not understand or could not contribute to, for that reason.

19. What practices and tools are in place for supply chain attacks mitigation for your projects?

This question seeks to understand current practices for mitigating supply chain attacks through project dependencies in FOSS/OSS.

In terms of practices, I think the main one we see in Django is that Django always tracks the development of upstream python. This means that they will find out about CVEs and security fixes as soon as they happen. Another important practice is the review culture. PRs are reviewed by many sets of eyes to verify they meet the highest standards of quality that they can.

20. Have any of the projects you have worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

Not that I know of.

21. What factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Being part of the contributing community

22. What challenges do you face which hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Addressing vulnerabilities, when it means migrating to better maintained dependencies always means several hours of work of familiarising oneself with the newer dependency, picking something else, and rewriting code and tests to match that dependency. Tests are especially challenging. One always wants to see them passing with good coverage and tries to avoid anything that would cause failures. So I'd say one of the biggest challenges is migrating dependencies. Because migrating is expensive, I tend to prefer using mature technology for the core of my applications, with less established projects being used only for small features. This makes it easy to change the vulnerable dependencies later, since they would not affect a large part of the code.

23. What recommendations do you have for FOSS/OSS dependency management to mitigate supply chain attacks?

Pick “boring” (mature, dependable, secure and well-tested) technology for the core of your applications to minimise the risk of supply chain attacks.

24. Do you have anything else you might want to add with regard to dependency management in FOSS/OSS projects to ensure FOSS/OSS security?

I think the more people contribute to open source, (hoping they would be experienced engineers and not all LLM agents!) the more set of eyes we have for reviews and tests, and the less likely we are to have vulnerabilities. So let's do more open source!

Thank you!